

THE COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ADJECTIVES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES.

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the usage and draws an analogy to adjectives by the levels of morphology in two different languages. Adjectives are seen in particularly different ways by Eastern and Western linguists, and even within setting to set side by side in order to show differences and likenesses. The past is over, but present you can seize, and make it for you in the immediate future. So, there are some similar and different features of adjectives which we have tried to demonstrate in English and Uzbek languages.

Keywords: adjectives, comparison, derivational, compound, superlative

Introduction. Language can differ in many ways. It may be used for different sounds, making voice in different ways, putting words together to form a sentence in different ways. In discussion of language and education, language is usually defined as a shared set of verbal codes, such as English, Russian, and Uzbek. But language can also be defined as a generic, communicative phenomenon, especially in description of instruction. Morphology is the general category that can be typologically compared in both English and Uzbek languages. In the morphological process occur to English adjective, there are some classes of word which can be modified by either derivational or inflectional affixes to form the grammatical category of adjective. Comparison is the act or the process of comparing. Such as a) the representing of one thing or person as similar to or like another, b) an examination of two or more items to establish similarities and dissimilarities. Comparative typology of various related and unrelated language is one of the significant achievements of Uzbek linguistics. Some linguists state that linguistic typology is also called cross-linguistic typology that deals with the analysis, comparison, and classification of languages according to their common structural features and forms. The main event in this field is the international conference held in April, 1961 in New York. In 1966 there appeared J.Greenberg's book "Language universals with special references to feature hierarchies". These works were followed by a number of other research works published as articles and special volumes. An adjective modifies a noun or pronoun by providing descriptive or specific detail. Unlike adverbs, adjectives do not modify verbs, other adjectives or adverbs. Adjectives usually precede the noun or pronoun they modify. Adjectives do not have to agree in number or gender with the nouns they describe.

Morphology is the study of words, how they are formed, and their relationship to other words in the same language. It analyses the structure of words such as stems, root words, prefixes, and suffixes. In the twentieth century the term was extended to the branch of grammar that investigates the structure of words which investigates the sentence structure. Morphological typology is a way of classifying the languages of the world group languages on the basis of how those languages form by combining morphemes. The primary categories exist to distinguish all languages: analytic languages and synthetic languages, where each term refers

to the opposite end of a continuous scale including all the world's languages. Often it is possible to identify units of meaning or grammatical function that morphemes. For example, the Uzbek word *kelmayapman* can be analyzed thus: *Kel-ma-yap-man* Come-neg.-progressive-1st person singular "I am not coming" An adjective, in grammar, is a word whose main syntactic role is to modify a noun or pronoun (called the adjective's subject), giving more information about reference what noun or pronoun. Collectively, adjectives form one of the traditional eight parts of speech, though linguists today distinguish adjectives from words such as determiners that used to be considered adjectives but that are now recognized as different. It derives from the Latin words *ad* and *acer* (Latin words that starts with an I change to a J in English). Many linguists have worked on the adjective deeply. For instance, Thus, in the long/short pair of gradable antonyms, long is unmarked (and short is marked) by the fact, according to Miller and Fellbaum (1991) and Bierwisch (1967) but not at least, not in the same meaning: 1.The train was ten cars long. 2.*The train was ten cars short. Comparative typology compares the systems of two or more concrete languages and creates common typological laws. The first comparative vowel tables appeared in the 19th century. Their aim was to prove the common origin of some two modern languages belonging to the same family. In the 1920s of the XX century Prof.D.Jones suggested a classification based on the principle of the so called <>. But these cardinal vowels are abstract notion and have nothing to do with the comparison of two language from the typological viewpoint. Now we will see and analyze some kind of differences. Results and discussion In both English and Uzbek languages the adjective qualifies or modifies a substance: English Uzbek a red apple- *qizil olma* , a clever student-*aqlli talaba*, a new building-*yangi bino*, red pepper- *qizil qalampir*. In the languages compared the adjective has the grammatical category of the degrees of comparison and typical stem building morphemes: English adjectives: a- (amoral), ab- (abnormal), demi- (demi season), di-(diatomic), dia- (diachronic), extra- (extraordinary), il-/im- /in-/ir-(illegal), immature, inadmissible, irrelative, post- (post- free), pre- (prechristian), un- (unpleasant), - able/ible (valuable, flexible), -al(natural), -an/- ean /- ian (American, Mediterranean, cyclopedian), - ant (disputant), -ary (revolutionary), -ate (elaborate) -ed (talented), -en (silken), -esque (grotesque), -fold (twofold), -ful (careful), -ic (syllabic), -ish (bluish), -ive (impulsive), -less (homeless), -like (childlike), -ly (tigerly),- most (heedmost), -tory / -ory (explanatory, modulatory), -ous (furious), -some (lonesome), -y (shady), -ical (logical). Uzbek adjectives: ba- (badavlat), be- (beg'am), bo- (boadab), no- (noaniq), bad- (badnafs),- li (kuchli), -siz (kuchsiz), -gi, -ki, -qi (tunggi, chillaki,tashqi), -dagi (ruldagi), -chan, / -chang (ishchan, ko'ylakchang), -chil (epchil), iy- (nazariy), -simon (odamsimon), -ik, / -iq,/ -uq (egik, qiyshiq, quruq), -ma (ezma), -qoq / - g'oq (tarqoq, toyg'oq), -choq, / -chiq (erinchoq, qizg'anchiq), -kir, / -qir (o'tkir, chopqir), -g'on (bilag'on), -iv (intensiv), -ik (demokratik), -al (aktual). In English and Uzbek the adjective usually forms combinations with:

1. nouns: Eng.: an interesting book, a tall tree, a strong man etc. Uzb.: qiziqarli kitob, baland daraxt etc. 2. link-verbs: Eng.: was strong, was clever, was old Uzb.: kuchli edi, aqlli edi, qari edi

3. adverbs: Eng.: very interesting, very old Uzb.: juda qiziqarli, juda eski. In English the adjective can combine with the so-called prop word " one" (the red one, the yellow one). In the languages compared the typical functions of the adjective are those of attribute and predicate: The adjective as an attribute: Eng.: I have brought him an interesting book. Uzb.: Men unga qiziqarli kitob olib keldim.

4. The adjective as a predicative .Eng.: The book was interesting. Uzb.: Kitob qiziqarli edi. According to their structure English and Uzbek adjectives may be:

1. simple: Eng.: red, good, hot, cold, slow Uzb: qizil, yaxshi, issiq, sovuq, sekin
2. derivative: Eng.: passive, talented, social, snowy Uzb,: noaktiv, talantli, kirishimli,qorli
3. compound: Eng.: big-eyed, deaf-mute, eagle-eyed, never-ending Uzb.: xushbo'y, vatanparvar, uchburchakli, odamsimon

On the base of their meaning adjectives are grouped into qualitative and relative classes. Qualitative adjectives express the property of nouns by means of special words denoting: opinion, colour, size,shape or physical quality, taste, smell, age, origin, material, qualifier/purpose etc. Eng.: good, wide, small, thin, thick, fat, clever, green, blue, red, little, big, dry, pale, glad, happy, hot, sick, ill, long, fluent, blunt, sharp, high, small, right, wrong etc. Uzb.: katta, keng, sariq, semiz, qari, tez,teng,tentak, tekis, tetik, tik, tinch, tirik, tortinchiq, achchiq, sassiq, shirin, mazali, bemaza, iflos, yorug'. Qualitative adjectives are characterized by the following common features.

1. Many stems of adjectives are used to form adverbs: English Uzbek wide-widely yangi-yangicha fluent-fluently ko'p-ko'pincha sharp-sharply qator-qatorasiga
2. Qualitative adjectives have the degrees of comparison: Positive Comparative Superlative English sweet sweeter sweetest High higher higher Happy happier happiest Uzbek keng kengroq eng keng Qora qoraroq eng qora Relative adjectives express properties characterizing an object through its reference to another object. Eng.: excessive, frontless, Indian, individual, fundamental, risky, homeless, floppy, gold, silky, mental etc. Uzb.: tushunarli, tuganmas, tashlandiq, temirbeton, temirday, so'zsiz, terma, taqlidiy, tekin, ijodiy,subutli, sevinchli etc.

Relative adjectives differ according to their meaning. They denote properties of nouns related to:

1. Inanimate nouns which are concrete or abstract: a diamond ring – brilliant uzuk etc.
2. Animate nouns expressing persons, animals, birds: eagle eye, tovuq miya etc.
3. Animate and inanimate nouns expressing locality or position: field flowers-dala gullari etc.
4. Animate and inanimate flowers expressing time: autumn wheat- kuzgi bug'doy etc.
5. Verbal adjectives expressing action or state: sleeping beauty-uyqudagi malik etc. In both languages many nouns can function as nouns and as adjectives.

In English, if it is compared with something, it denotes equal quality of those things compared: David is as clever as Mike. David is as stupid as Mike. The comparative degree is morphologically marked in both languages. In English it expresses a higher or less degree of quality of the thing expressed by the subject in relation to the thing with which it is compared. Depending on the length of the adjective it is formed by two ways: 1) By adding the affix -er to short adjectives: long-longer etc. 2) By putting the words more or less before long adjectives: beautiful-more beautiful, beautiful-less beautiful etc. In Uzbek it is formed by adding the affix - roq to the adjective: uzun-uzunroq, chiroyli-chiroyliroq etc. The affix -roq means a little/a bit more or a little/a bit less: Uzb.;Meri Annadan chiroyliroq Eng.:Mary is a (little) bit more beautiful than Anna. In Uzbek the positive degree is functionally equal to the positive and comparative degrees. Compare : David is clever=David aqli. David is clever than Mike=David Maykday aqli. The superlative degree expresses the highest (least) degree of the quality denoted by the adjective stem with the suffix -est and the structures most+ adj. and least +adj. in English and the structure eng+adj. in Uzbek: Mary is the most beautiful girl=Meri eng

chiroyli qiz David is the cleverest boy= Devid eng aqlli bola. There are some adjectives in English whose comparative and superlative degrees are formed by changing the root: Simple Comparative Superlative Good-yaxshi better-yaxshiroq the best-eng yaxshi Bad-yomon worse-yomonroq the worst-eng yomon

Little-oz less-ozroq the least-eng kam

Much/many-ko'p more-ko'proq the most-eng ko'p

Far adjective has two types in forming:

Positive ,Comparative ,Superlative . Far-uzoq farther-uzoqroq the farthest-eng uzoq Further-uzoqroq, the furthest-eng uzoq, eng keyingi Keyingi, qo'shimcha The word enough which shows the quantity of something or state differs in using in both languages: In Uzbek "yetarlicha" comes before adjective. e.g. Qalin jaketni kiyish uchun hali yetarlicha sovuq emas. But in English the word "enough" comes after adjective. e.g. It is not cold enough to wear a heavy jacket. In addition, the English conjunction "no sooner..., than..." is used to denote simultaneous actions. It is the negative of 'as soon as'.

In English: No sooner had she entered the building, than she felt the presence of somebody else. In Uzbek: U binoga kirar-kirmasdan, u yerda yana kimningdir borligini his qildi. Comparing the usage we identified that the construction in Uzbek grammar is different which used as 'participle'. Moreover, the singular form of English and Uzbek nouns is zero morpheme. We add suffix in both languages in order to make a plural form. We also can see some distinctive features of parts of speech in these languages while English have root exchange in forming degrees of adjectives, in Uzbek we have suffix -lar which means respect for adults: onamlar and so on. It should be noted that classification of adjective is considered as problematic in the other compared language. Therefore, there are different approaches in classifying them into groups.

Conclusions. Morphological unit plays an essential role to learn e.g. reading texts easily, gives vocabulary knowledge to identify words and recognize their meanings while they engage with the learning word or reading one. The adjective - a grammatical part of speech modifies and describes a noun. Furthermore, it tells some descriptive ideas of the noun and they are: size, color, shape, origin, state, character and etc. Because of the differences of geographic environment of the two nations, the grammatical structures of the part of speech – there are some differences in forming the words of adjectives, adding the prefixes and suffixes, forming of comparison degrees and etc. Some adjectives may have more one field, so it is difficult to define the made words from the root ones. The distinctive feature of Uzbek language word formation way is composition which can not be found in other compared languages. Finally, from the analysis of compared languages can be found several similarities, it is possible to show the existence of types of affixation in both languages, or amount of derived words or suffixes, which can change the meaning from one part of speech into another.

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